

TEACHING FOR READING TEXTS AT SCHOOLS

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In this article there was written about teaching for reading texts at schools. Reading comprehension is often the main goal of learners in countries where English is taught as a foreign language. Moreover, reading can be considered as a primary source of language input, a Pleasurable activity, and a means of extending one's knowledge of language.

Key words: methodologies, vocabulary learning, reading comprehension, language input.

The current rapidly changing time, when competition on the world arises, requires us all to think in a new way, to work with even greater impact.

Proceeding from these tasks, in order to raise the development of our country to a new, higher level, we adopted the Strategy of Action on the five priority development directions of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021.

In this Strategy, improvement of state and social construction, ensuring the rule of law and reforming the judicial and legal system, further development of the economy and social sphere, ensuring security, interethnic harmony and religious tolerance are defined as the main directions, continuing a deeply thought out foreign policy based on the principles of constructive dialogue and mutually beneficial cooperation.

In the Strategy of Action, the principle "It is not the people that serves state bodies, but the state bodies should serve the people" is defined as one of the highest priorities of state policy.

Uzbekistan is a secular state with a great future, which is famous for its customs and traditions, kind, compassionate and multicultural nation which will help in difficult times, share shelter and bread.

On the territory of our country science and culture have evolved from ancient times. Thousands of scientists and thinkers lived and worked here. Their scientific heritage, as well as the architectural monuments of those days in Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva, Tashkent, Shahrisabz, Termez and other towns are still the spiritual wealth of all mankind.

In Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to education of harmoniously developed young generation. Activities on creating necessary conditions for youth in receiving modern education are being consistently continued.

President of our country noted the need to strengthen relations between schools and colleges, in particular, reconstitution in the experimental order of the 11-year educational system in this school, establishment of a vocational training under the school.

Children are formed as individuals, unifying in a team in high school classes, said the head of our state. During this period they should not be excommunicated from an adapted, habitual for them environment. This can negatively affect the psychology of youth, their

attendance at school, and ultimately – on the level of education and upbringing. Therefore, it is necessary to ensure the continuity of the educational process, improve training programs.

President of our Republic SH.M.Mirziyoyev is paying great attention to higher education system of Uzbekistan. On April 20, 2017 he signed a decree PQ 2909 “On the measures of further development of the system of higher education.” The aim of this decree is to improve the system of higher education, to review the contents of preparing cadres according to the priority tasks of social-economical development of the country, to establish conditions for preparing higher educational specialists suit for international standards. [1, 1-3]

Priority of our state for today is to rear educated, harmoniously developed generation. To do this, the country created the necessary conditions: every citizen of Uzbekistan is guaranteed free, medical care. The law secures that the 12-year education in Uzbekistan is mandatory and free for all, and is conditioned by the fact that the growing generation is obliged to receive a 12-year education, attain a concrete vocation and profession. After 12-year compulsory education everyone by his or her choice can continue study at higher education institutions to obtain undergraduate and graduate degrees.

At present great importance is attached to the study and teaching of foreign languages. No doubt, it happens not without purpose. Today, the importance of our people’s perfect knowledge of foreign language can scarcely be exaggerated as our country aspires to win a decent place in the world community, because our people see their great future as a life in mutual accord and cooperation with their foreign fathers.

That is why it is necessary to improve the current situation, to provide Uzbek children with all the necessary conditions for the access to this amazing world of foreign languages.

We should prepare in our country in the shortest time the methods of intensive foreign language learning based on our national peculiarities.

Methodological recommendations for reading texts given in the book fly high is very important in the teaching English texts. In most existing methodologies vocabulary learning has been the center of attention but this component of language has been treated in various ways. In Grammar Translation Method, "much vocabulary is taught in the form of lists of isolated words. Other methods favor context – bound vocabulary learning. Reading comprehension is often the main goal of learners in countries where English is taught as a foreign language. Moreover, reading can be considered as a primary source of language input, a Pleasurable activity, and a means of extending one's knowledge of language. In recent years, authorities in the field of teaching English have rejected the notion of learning vocabulary out of context. Richards stated that words are organized in to an intricate, interlocking system: therefore, they cannot be learned in isolation without considering their related context.

Reading is type of speech activity and the goal of teaching at all stages. A person may read in order to gain information or verify existing knowledge, or in order to critique a writer's ideas or writing style. A person may also read for enjoyment, or to enhance knowledge of the language being read. The goal(s) for reading guide the reader's selection of texts.

In methodology of FLT the qualities of good readers are described as follows:

- Read extensively;
- Integrate information in the text with existing knowledge;
- Have a flexible reading style, depending on what they are reading, are motivated;
- Rely on different skills interacting: perceptual processing, phonemic processing, recall;

- Read for a purpose; reading serves a function;
- Strategies that can help pupils read more quickly and effectively include;
- Previewing: reviewing titles, section headings, and photo captions to get a sense of the structure and content of a reading selection;
- Predicting: using knowledge of the subject matter to make predictions about content and vocabulary and check comprehension; using knowledge of the text type and purpose to make predictions about discourse structure; using knowledge about the author to make predictions about writing style, vocabulary, and content;
- Skimming and scanning: using a quick survey of the text to get the main idea, identify text structure, confirm or question predictions;
- Guessing from context: using prior knowledge of the subject and the ideas in the text as clues to the meanings of unknown words, instead of stopping to look them up;
- Paraphrasing: stopping at the end of a section to check comprehension by restating the information and ideas in the text.

Methodical recommendations to develop reading skills in the early grades of primary school as a way to produce reliable information that can be used to guide policymaking, strengthen accountability, and ultimately improve quality of education.

Fluent readers are more likely to understand what they read than non-fluent readers. However, results suggest that this relationship is discontinuous and non-linear. Advancing a new analytical approach, the authors find that the strength of this relationship depends on the level of fluency, the difficulty of the questions, and certain social characteristics such as first language of the child.

At the early stages of learning to read, fluency is crucial and can only be developed by practicing. The test itself, more than a measure, is also an opportunity to practice and to keep the focus on results. It is relatively easy to administer and gives the teachers information on which students/pupils require more attention and which ones are making good progress. It also gives parents information on the progress of their children at school. Even an illiterate parent is able to discern whether his or her child can or cannot read fluently, as the sound of a non-fluent reader is unmistakable.

In conclusion, it is not only possible but also desirable to use improved versions of both tests as tools to encourage, monitor and evaluate the development of reading skills in the early grades.

It can be presented, explained, and included in all kinds of activities to be learned by individuals. The vocabulary we understand and the vocabulary we can use very in nature and in quantity from one person to another even in our native language. We can help our students/pupils/pupils by giving those ideas on how to learn vocabulary and some guidance on what to learn.

Methods of reading skills give similar results. Another words, children who read more fluently have better chances of understanding what they read.

Teaching approaches that have proven more effective for early reading; the different instruments used to assess reading performance; the correlations between fluency and comprehension measures; what criteria to use when choosing between oral and written reading texts; and the differential behavior of texts and items in different populations.

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